

EFFECTS OF HERBICIDES ON GROWTH AND REPRODUCTION OF THE EARTHWORMS

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Scientific literature discussing the impact of herbicides on growth and reproduction is reviewed. Herbicides have become most used substance to control weeds. The herbicides are used in large amount by the farmers in the field without examining the side effects of these herbicides on soil organisms. The herbicides residues may create adverse effects on the environment by leaching to ground water and give rise to water pollution. It is believed that where herbicides are used to control weeds, they are considered harmful to soil organisms by increase mortality and reduce reproduction of organisms. Earthworm is known as farmer's friend because they improve the quality of soil. The effect of herbicides on earthworm depends on type and concentration of herbicide. This review will outline the state of knowledge about the harmful effects of herbicides to soil biotic community.

INTRODUCTION:

In developed countries, herbicides account for more than 70% of total pesticides available in the market (Muthukaruppan *et al.*, 2005). Herbicide use is increasing both in agriculture and private gardens. Although, our knowledge of side effects on non-target soil organism even on such eminent ones as earthworms, is still very limited (Mailin Gaupp-Berghausen *et al.*, 2015). The enormous use of herbicides is responsible for the degradation of agro ecosystem sustainability (Celine *et al.*, 2014). The low cost of herbicides compared to other strategies inspire farmers to use the chemical method to control weeds (Zarea *et al.*, 2010). The use of herbicides does not affect only weeds, herbicides can also destroy non-target species in the agricultural fields and also affect the physiochemical properties of soil (Robidoux *et al.*, 1999). To minimize weeds problem in crops, the application of herbicides should be on a regular action. (Nada *et al.*, 2010). Herbicides in general show low toxicity towards worms, despite there are some exceptions (Zarea, 2010). This review will outline the state of knowledge about the harmful effects of herbicides to soil biotic community.

Earthworms are an important part of the soil system, and can promote plant growth by improving soil fertility and nutrient cycling (Lee 1985). Earthworms are generally used as test organisms because of their important function, for example, as decomposer (C.A. Edwards *et al.*,1996). Earthworms are used to check out the lethal and sub-lethal effects of contaminants and pollutants (Muthukaruppan Gobi *et al.*,2010). Although, earthworm species may vary in their tolerance, reports have shown a decrease in earthworm populations in response to large amounts of organic chemical deposition (D.E. Bayer *et al.*,1982).

Brown (1978) reported that some herbicides are directly toxic to earthworms while others have effectually no effects. It is advised that the chronic test, focusing at sublethal effects, is more sensitive and is more practical approach for the prediction of environmental effects because in the field, the exposure concentrations of pesticides are low (Rombke *et al.*,2007). The biochemical responses constitute a supportive approach to standard toxicity tests in the valuation of sub-lethal effect of pollutants in earthworms, offering information about the stress response in the organism and toxic action of the chemical (Rico *et al.*,2016).

Herbicides not only cause in some instances, but it can also influence the function, growth, reproduction and the health of earthworms. So, it is important to be aware about the possible effect that any chemicals may have on earthworms before applying it to the crops (Dr. Maryke Craven *et al.*,2018).

Effect on growth of earthworm

A number of studies have been conducted on earthworm. (Chen *et al.* 2014b) studied the combined toxicity of butachlor, atrazine and k-cyhalothrin on the earthworm *Eisenia fetida* by combination index (CI)-isobologram method in artificial soil by filter paper tests. The order of toxicity of the pesticides was ranked as atrazine > k-cyhalothrin > butachlor in both tests. They observed that synergism was found in majority of the mixtures except for the combination of butachlor plus k-cyhalothrin for most cases in artificial soil test. This combination showed opposite interaction in filter paper test. (Hattab *et al.*, 2015) considered the stress response of earthworms (*Eisenia andrei*) to exposure to a commonly used herbicide, 2,4 dichloro-phenoxy-acetic acid (2,4-D). They exposed the earthworms to three concentration of 2,4-D (3.5, 7, and 14 mg/kg) for 7 and 14 days. Results showed that the exposure to 7 and 14 mg/kg of 2,4-D significantly reduced both the body weight and lysosomal membrane stability of the earthworm. (Herman Uwizeyimana *et al.*,2018) investigated the ecotoxicological effects of binary mixtures of siduron and Cd on mRNA expression in the earthworm *Eisenia fetida*. *Eisenia fetida* gene expressions including metallothionein (MT) and heat shock protein70 (Hsp70) were analyzed using real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction after individual and combined siduron. The results revealed variations in MT and weak changes in Hsp70 expression when the earthworms were exposed to individual Cd. (Singh *et al.*, 2015) reported the toxic effects of herbicide 2,4-D on the earthworm *Eutyphoeus waltoni* was both time and dose dependent. Maximum toxicity was observed in the sandy

soil, minimum in the feed material of buffalo dung with gram bran. (Andreu *et al.*, 2016) studied the effects of five pesticides generally used in rice farming (trichlorfon, dimethoate, carbendazim, tebuconazole and prochloraz) was evaluated on different lethal and sub-lethal endpoints of the earthworm *Eisenia fetida*. They observed endpoints included: avoidance behaviour after an exposure period and mortality, weight loss, enzymatic activities (cholinesterase, lactate dehydrogenase and alkaline phosphatase) and histopathological effects after an exposure period of 14 days.

The observed effects on the enzymatic activities in *Eisenia fetida* and they also observed histopathological alterations (longitudinal and circular muscle lesions, edematous tissues, endothelial degeneration and necrosis). (Shubham More *et al.*, 2021) introduced that heavy metals, insecticide and herbicide induced behavioural and physiological changes in the earthworm *Eisenia fetida*. Behavioural changes in the earthworm, as well as morphological changes and the time for the onset of mortality was observed. (Dereddy Gangadhar *et al.*, 2021) studied the effects of Alachlor Herbicide on *Eisenia fetida* and Its Biochemical Responses. *E. fetida* were treated with LC50 concentration of alachlor for 24 h. Significant changes in morphology like whole body coiling, fragmentation, and thinning of body and clitellar shrinkage were noticed in *E. fetida* exposed to alachlor for 24 h. (Sharon Pochron *et al.* 2019) determined which factors drive earthworm sensitivity. They found that both earthworm responses varied with intrinsic worm characteristics and environmental characteristics. Worms of lighter mass and worms grown in a cooler temperature did not respond to contamination by altering final body mass. Earthworm sensitivity varies with specific environmental and somatic conditions.

Effects on reproduction of earthworm

(Muthukaruppan *et al.*, 2010) studied the effects of exposure to commercial herbicide Butachlor on the life history parameters (clitellum development, and cocoon production) and the histological changes in the earthworm *Eisenia fetida* in 60 days, The mean earthworm biomass was found to be decreased with increase in the concentration of herbicide. Similarly, cocoon production was also reduced by the increase in the concentration of herbicide. All earthworms exposed were found to have glandular cell enlargement and to be vacuolated. (Correia and Moreira, 2010) studied the effects of various concentrations of glyphosate and 2,4-D on earthworms (*Eisenia fetida*) cultured in argosol during 56 days of incubation. The impact on earthworm's growth, survival, and reproduction rates were verified at different exposure times. They found that there was no mortality in glyphosate treated soil samples, but showed significant reduction in mean weight (50%) at all test concentrations. For 2,4-D, 100% mortality was found in soil treated with 500 and 1,000 mg/kg. At 14 days, 30%-40% mortality levels were observed in all other concentrations. They observed no cocoons or juveniles in soil treated with either herbicide. They concluded that glyphosate and 2,4-D demonstrated effects the development and reproduction of *Eisenia fetida*. (Chen *et al.*, 2014) observed the acute toxicity of butachlor, imidacloprid and chlorpyrifos with different modes of action on earthworm, *Eisenia fetida*. They compared the

ecotoxicities of these pesticides for earthworm *Eisenia fetida* separately and in combination in artificial soil by contact filter paper tests. They observed that imidacloprid was the most toxic for *Eisenia fetida* with LC 50 (lethal concentration 50) values three orders magnitude lower than that of butachlor and chlorpyrifos in both tests. They compared toxicity of the mixtures by the concentration addition (CA) model and found the observed toxicities of all binary mixtures were less than additive. (Mailin Gaupp-Berghausen *et al.* 2015) studied the effect of glyphosate-based herbicide on the activity and reproduction of different earthworm species. They found that the surface casting activity of vertically burrowing earthworms (*Lumbricus terrestris*) almost ended three weeks after herbicide application, while the activity of soil dwelling earthworms (*Aporrectodea caliginosa*) was not affected. Reproduction of the soil dwellers was reduced by 56% within three months after herbicide application. (Dominguez *et al.* 2016) studied the toxic effect of aminomethyl phosphonic acid (AMPA) on the earthworm *Eisenia andrei*. They find that earthworms from parents grown in contaminated soils may have reduced growth, limiting their beneficial roles in soil ecosystem functions.

(Devorka K. Hackenberger *et al.* 2018) studied the acute and subchronic effects of herbicides on biomarker response and reproduction in earthworm. Three different herbicides glyphosate (GLF), tembotrione (TBT) and nicosulfuron (NCS) each applied at three environmentally relevant concentrations have adverse effects on various biomarkers and reproduction in epigenic earthworm *Dendrobaena veneta*. Their result showed that the herbicides can influence earthworm' survival, physiology and reproduction. (Krishan Kumar and Pooja Kumawat 2018) studied effects of herbicides on earthworms. They found that the use of herbicides can affect the biological parameters of earthworms. There was a precise impact on biomass and cocoon production after the application of herbicides at different concentrations. The review highlighted that some herbicides are harmful and are highly toxic to earthworms. (Sofia Lammertyn *et al.* 2021) studied the Biomarkers response and population biological parameters in the earthworm *Eisenia fetida* after short term exposure to atrazine herbicide. In this work, earthworms (*Eisenia fetida*) were exposed to different concentrations of atrazine to find possible harmful effects. The lower atrazine concentration (2 mg Kg⁻¹) affected in shortest term (7 days) the rate of cocoon production and increased LDH activity.

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